

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Milestone 1 Target Enabling Package

Evaluation of Apoptosis-associated Speck-like Protein Containing a CARD (ASC) for Alzheimer's Drug Discovery

Gene	PYD and CARD domain containing
Symbol	PYCARD
Alternatives	TMS, TMS-1, TMS1, ASC, CARD5
NCBI Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	29108 / Q9ULZ3 / ENSG00000103490
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Abstract

The TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) centers were established to provide high-quality research tools and technologies to validate and advance the next generation of drug targets for Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Data, methods, and computational and experimental tools are being openly disseminated to the broader AD research community for use in drug discovery research to better understand the complex biology of AD. These resources and others are made available in a Target Enablement Package (TEP) at the Synapse AD Knowledge Portal.

Here the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center is providing a TEP focused on *PYCARD*, the gene *PYD* and *CARD* domain containing, and its protein product ASC, apoptosis-associated speck-like protein containing a *CARD*. We evaluate *PYCARD* mRNA and ASC protein expression across cells and tissues. The protein structures and domains of ASC are described in detail. Pharmacological assays relevant to the biology of ASC are discussed. We also evaluate existing molecules reported to interact with ASC protein and a perspective on its druggability.

Introduction to the target ASC and its potential involvement in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's Disease

The gene *PYCARD* codes for the protein ASC which functions as a molecular scaffolding protein component of the inflammasome. Inflammasomes are innate immune protein complexes that evolved to assemble in response to specific environmental or cellular stimuli especially those associated with cellular damage or infections¹. The assembly of the inflammasome protein complex is initiated by the binding of sensor proteins, such as NLRP3 or AIM2, to their respective ligands. Binding of an inflammasome sensor protein to its ligand initiates the inflammasome assembly process by recruiting the scaffolding protein ASC through its *PYD* domain to nucleate into fibril structures² (**Figure 1**). ASC protein fibrils recruit protein caspases through *CARD* domains leading to caspase-1 activation. This protein assembly and recruitment process results in the formation of the large paranuclear ASC aggregate or speck. Super resolution imaging of ASC proteins reveals a striking redistribution of diffuse ASC proteins to dense speck structures upon stimulation in THP-1 cells³. The activated caspase enzymes in the inflammasome complex proteolytically processes cytokines to their active forms including the cytokines IL-1 β and IL-18. This role of inflammasome dependent cytokine processing is impaired in *PYCARD* knockout mice, which are viable but have impaired processing of both IL-1 β and IL-18 while other cytokines including TNF α are not affected⁴. This caspase and cytokine activation mechanism can be blocked in a cell-free system using ASC targeting antibodies⁵. The inflammasome can also initiate pyroptosis or inflammatory cell death in which pores of gasdermin D (GSDMD) protein form in the cellular membrane⁶. Membrane rupture leads to the release of ASC specks into the

Figure 1. The NLRP3 inflammasome signaling pathway. Activation of discrete immune signaling receptors results in “priming” of the inflammasome by increasing transcription on inflammasome associated genes, including ASC. A secondary activation signal then initiates the rapid assembly of the multi-protein inflammasome complex.

extracellular space where they can continue to exert biological activity and may serve to perpetuate inflammation where they act as a mechanism of immune signal propagation⁷.

Neuroinflammation is an established feature of Alzheimer’s disease (AD) pathophysiology, and genes known to regulate NLRP3 activation have been identified as genetic risk factors for AD⁸. Increased levels of cleaved IL-1β and NLRP3 inflammasome activation have been detected in AD patient brains⁹⁻¹¹. In transgenic mouse models of AD, deletion of NLRP3 reduces plaque burden and improves cognition¹². It has been shown that NLRP3 itself can be activated in LPS treated primary microglia by aggregated amyloid beta, which may serve as one mechanism of inflammasome activation in the AD brain^{13,14}. However, it should be noted that one study found no effect upon NLRP3 disruption in transgenic AD rodent models, suggesting that inflammasome activity is dispensable for Aβ pathology in this context¹⁵. This apparent discrepancy highlights the complexity of inflammasome signaling in microglial activation and the importance of AD disease states and other contextual factors.

ASC specks may be of importance in AD by acting as molecular seeds of amyloid plaques. ASC specks have been shown to enhance Aβ aggregation and intrahippocampal injection of ASC specks into an AD mouse model increased the number and area of amyloid plaques. Moreover, fluorescent imaging revealed the presence of ASC protein in AD patient amyloid plaque deposits¹⁶. Total ASC protein levels in AD patient serum are higher than in control patients¹⁷.

Interestingly, ASC specks may have some value as a biomarker of neurodegeneration because ASC specks are more abundant in the serum and CSF of AD and Parkinson's disease patients compared to healthy controls¹⁸. Furthermore, ASC fibrils have been shown to enhance the toxicity of A β and promote pyroptosis of primary microglial cells, potentially contributing to toxic inflammation¹⁹.

Taken together, we propose that targeting ASC may have disease modifying efficacy by modulating inflammasome formation and subsequent downstream cytokine maturation, and through the disruption of ASC protein speck formation in brain tissue.

Expression of PYCARD mRNA and ASC protein across tissues and microglial subtypes

The *PYCARD* gene is conserved across species, including both mice and humans. In both species, *PYCARD* is predominantly expressed in immune-related tissues, such as lymphoid tissues and bone marrow, underscoring its involvement in immune responses. Notably, in the healthy brain, *PYCARD* expression is relatively low in both humans and mice, suggesting a limited role in central nervous system functions under normal, non-inflammatory conditions.

In mice, a single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) in the 3' untranslated region (UTR) of the *PYCARD* gene has been shown to affect mRNA stability and protein expression levels, thereby influencing inflammasome activity²⁰. This SNP leads to increased *PYCARD* mRNA stability and higher ASC protein levels, resulting in enhanced inflammasome activation.

Figure 2. RNA expression of *PYCARD* in multiple tissues quantified in normalized transcripts per million (nTPM), integrating RNA-seq data from the Human Protein Atlas (HPA) and the Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) project.

ASC protein in humans has three alternative isoforms resulting from differential splicing, referenced in UniProt as Q9ULZ3, as Q9ULZ3-1, Q9ULZ3-2, and Q9ULZ3-3. Notably, one splice variant lacks exon 2, which is observed under specific conditions, such as certain inflammatory responses²¹. Additionally, *PYCARD* has 236 genetic variants listed in UniProt, which can be evaluated for somatic occurrence and impact levels. However, the clinical significance of these variants and mutations remains largely unknown.

Figure3. *PYCARD* RNA gene expression levels across different brain regions reported as Log2 counts per million (CPM) as reported on the Agora AD Knowledge Portal. ACC (Anterior Cingulate Cortex), CBE (Cerebellum), DLPFC (Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex), FP (Frontal Pole), IFG (Inferior Frontal Gyrus), PCC (Posterior Cingulate Cortex), PHG (Parahippocampal Gyrus), STG (Superior Temporal Gyrus), TCX (Temporal Cortex).

PYCARD exhibits varying expression levels across tissues as reported on the Human Protein Atlas website (**Figure 2**). Notably, *PYCARD* expression is highest in tissues such as spleen and bone marrow, emphasizing its tissue-enhanced specificity in immune-related organs and its potential role in regulating inflammatory responses and immune signaling pathways. This distinct pattern

Figure 4. Relative ASC protein levels across cell types in normalized transcripts per million (nTPM), as reported from Human Protein Atlas (HPA).

of expression underscores *PYCARD*'s dominant role in immune-related functions, while hinting at its specialized, context-dependent activity in other tissue systems.

PYCARD levels are detectable across several brain regions as reported on Agora AD Knowledge Portal (**Figure 3**). The highest mRNA levels are detected in anterior cingulate cortex and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, but some level of expression is observed through different brain regions. These transcriptional differences may result from the heterogeneity of cell types and tissue structures across the brain.

The Human Protein Atlas reports that ASC protein levels vary across cell types across various tissues (**Figure 4**). High expression levels are predominantly observed in immune and epithelial cells. In healthy brain tissue, moderate protein expression is seen in microglia cells, but nearly absent in neurons and astrocytes in a non-inflammatory state.

Given the established role of ASC in inflammasome biology and its relatively high expression in immune tissues, we evaluated *PYCARD* mRNA expression in microglia which serve as resident brain immune cells. Using existing data from a new study of microglia heterogeneity in AD, we evaluated the single cell expression of *PYCARD* in different human microglial subtypes²². Analysis of this dataset revealed statistically significant *PYCARD* expression levels across specific subtypes in microglia shown in **Table 1**. Homeostatic microglia, identified by the marker *PICALM*, expressed detectable levels of *PYCARD* though the relative abundance of this expression varied across fresh

Tissue	Subclass	Subtype	Log2FC	AUROC*	P value
Fresh	ADAM	GPNMB	0.536	0.556	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	AIF1	1.348	0.639	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	CCL3	0.416	0.544	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	HIF1A	-0.306	0.468	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	HSPA1A	-0.202	0.479	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	IFI44L	0.499	0.552	<0.001
Fresh	Homeostatic	PICALM	-0.202	0.479	<0.001
Fresh	PVM	CD163	-0.074	0.492	<0.001
Fresh	Proliferative	MKI67	0.675	0.570	<0.001
Fresh	exAM	ERN1	-1.211	0.375	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	HIF1A	-0.046	0.496	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	HSPA1A	-0.063	0.493	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	TMEM163	-0.057	0.494	<0.001
Frozen	Homeostatic	PICALM	0.022	0.502	<0.001

Table 1. Differential expression analysis of *PYCARD* for several microglial subtypes using log2FC as a measure of the relative change in gene expression between specific microglia subtype relative to all other microglia. *Area under ROC curve for the expression of *PYCARD* cell subtype prediction.

and frozen samples. Interestingly, *PYCARD* expression was significantly upregulated in some microglial subtypes including the *GPNMB* expressing subtype enriched in AD patient tissue samples. Other microglial subtypes with high relative *PYCARD* expression included the AIF1 and CCL3 adaptive subtypes which suggest *PYCARD* expression levels change in microglial during distinct activation states. *PYCARD* was significantly downregulated in several microglial subtypes including the Adaptive-*HIF1A* and Adaptive-*HSPA1A* microglia cells, along with PVM-*CD163* and exAM-*ENR1* and Adaptive-*TMEM163* in subtypes.

PYCARD has also been evaluated on the Agora AD Knowledge Portal. Driven in large part by a Multi-omic Score of 1.96 out of 2, the overall Target Risk Score is 3.28 out of 5 placing this gene in the top 20% of all analyzed and making *PYCARD* an attractive AD target.

ASC protein structure

ASC is ~24 kDa cytosolic protein comprised of mainly two domains: N-terminal pyrin domain (PYD) and C-terminal caspase recruitment domain (CARD) joined by 23 amino acid linker (**Figure 5A**). This long flexible linker allows for independent movement of the two domains, facilitating the binding of each to their respective partners. The full-length NMR structure of ASC shows six helix bundle of each PYD and CARD domain²³.

The AlphaFold3 model of full-length ASC indicates a high confidence score for both PYD and CARD domains, but less confident score (pIDDT<50) for the linker region. Structural alignment of the reported solution structure with the AlphaFold3 model shows almost complete overlap with PYD domain but not the CARD domain (RMSD = 1.031 Å). These differences are a consequence of the highly flexible loop connecting the two domains (**Figure 5B**).

On comparing the solution structure of ASC PYD domain with the cryo-EM structure² (**Figure 5C**), there is a slight difference in the positioning of helix4 (RMSD = 1.343 Å) and in case of CARD domain²⁴, there are differences in helix 1,4,5 and 6 (RMSD = 1.309 Å). We also compared both domains with the other proteins containing PYD and CARD domains. The PYD domain of NALP1²⁵ in contains long disordered loop instead of the helix 4 (RMSD = 1.191 Å) (**Figure 5D**). These changes suggest the possibility that these regions may play an important role in filament formation. Similarly, there are differences in the helices 1, 4 and 6 compared to the NLRP1 CARD domain²⁶ (RMSD = 1.152).

There are four isoforms of ASC due to alternative splicing of the *PYCARD* gene: ASC, ASCb, ASCc and ASCd. ASC, the canonical isoform, is the full-length protein (~22 kDa) containing both of the PYD and CARD domains. ASCb is similar to ASC, containing both domains, but the linker is only three amino acid long. ASCc and ASDd lack the full PYD or CARD domains. ASCc contains the CARD domain and a partial PYD domain, while the CARD domain is absent in ASCd. It has been shown that canonical ASC oligomerizes faster than ASCb²⁷. ASC oligomerizes into filamentous disks whereas ASCb self assembles in liner filaments. Despite structural similarity and 100% sequence

identity between ASC and ASCb, the NMR and DLS studies showed differences in the self-assembly of ASC and ASCb isoforms. In case of ASC, the PYD-PYD interactions initiate the self-assembly and then the CARD domains interact. In contrast, the PYD and CARD domains of ASCb interact equally to self-assemble. These differences in oligomerization indicate that the linker plays a crucial role in reorientation of the PYD and CARD domain of ASC^{2,27}. In addition to differences in the domain positioning, the kinetics of oligomerization also vary. RT-NMR studies on both these isoforms indicate that ASC undergoes a fast kinetic phase where the PYD-PYD interactions initiate the assembly followed by the CARD-CARD interactions, converting monomeric ASCs to oligomers and then in the second slower kinetic phase both PYD and CARD comes together to form the filaments. In ASCb the PYD and CARD domains interact equally to form filaments. ASC oligomerizes faster and in more uniform fashion whereas ASCb self-associates more slowly and forms disordered filaments²⁷.

Figure 5. Structure of full-length ASC protein and its structural comparison. **A.** Solution structure of full-length ASC, pink shows the PYD domain, blue shows the CARD domain and linker region is shown in cyan color (PDB: 2KN6). **B.** Solution structure of ASC superimposed with AlphaFold3 model of ASC (green). **C.** Solution structure of ASC superimposed with the individual cryo-EM structure of PYD (PDB: 3J63; dark pink) and CARD (PDB: 6N1H; orange) domains. **D.** Solution structure of ASC superimposed with the PYD domain of NALP1 in grey (PDB: 1PN5) and the CARD domain of NLRP1 in teal (PDB: 6K7V).

Crystallizing full-length ASC or even the individual domains is challenging. As a result, few X-ray crystal structures of ASC domains are available. In a recently published study, a crystal structure of human ASC CARD with the MBP (Maltose-binding protein) tag was shown. The MBP tag helps the protein to solubilize and prevents it from aggregation²⁸. A cryo-EM study of ASC revealed a 3.8 Å structure of the ASC PYD filament, demonstrating a unified assembly mechanism for inflammasomes through nucleation-induced filament formation. The PYD domain of sensor proteins like AIM2 and NLRP3 interacts with the ASC PYD, nucleating the helical cluster. Subsequently, the CARD domain of ASC nucleates caspase-1 by initiating CARD-CARD interactions. Additionally, it has been shown that the CARD domains of NLRs can also form filamentous structures by interacting directly with the CARD domain of caspase-1, independent of ASC². Another cryo-EM study shows the 3.17 Å filament structure of ASC CARD domain and also highlighted the nucleation assembly of filament formation. This study also showed the filament structure for another CARD domain containing protein called NLRC4 and indicated that both ASC CARD and NLRC4 CARD showed very similar structures and capable of activating caspase-1²⁴.

There are three interaction interfaces that are known to be involved in ASC oligomerization. Type 1 interface are interactions between the helices of PYD-PYD domain, Type2 and Type3 interface involve the helices-loop interactions. Different ASC mutations have been reported that have shown disruption in speck formation. Type I mutation includes K21A, K26A, D48N, D51R, Type II mutations are M76A, Y59A, Q79E and E80R, and Type III mutation involves L15A, E13R and R41E. Some mutations like L25A, D48A and R160A are suggested to compact the ASC speck assembly, while others (Q79E and E80R) have been reported to disrupt the speck assembly²⁹. Some residues in the CARD domain play a specific role in ASC speck formation and inflammasome assembly. CARD domain mutants like D128R, D132R and E144R have also been reported to disrupt ASC oligomerization thus resulting in non-functional inflammasome assembly. Similar to PYD interface, three interfaces (Type I, II and III) have been identified in CARD-CARD domain interactions. The ASC CARD filament structure suggested that in Type I interface residues (R119, E130, D134 and R160) involves the electrostatic interactions between the helices of the CARD domain (helix 2 of one molecule and helix 1 and 4 of other). Type II interface residues (W169 and Y187) involve hydrophobic interactions and Type III is same as Type I showing charge-charge interactions between R160 and D143 or E144²⁴.

A nanobody (variable heavy chain, VHH) has been reported to interact with the CARD domain of ASC, demonstrating that VHH binds to the ASC CARD interface, which is essential for ASC self-oligomerization and the recruitment of procaspase-1 through CARD-CARD interactions. To generate a monomeric ASC CARD, two residues (N128 and E130), predicted to impair CARD-CARD interactions, were mutated (N128A/E130R). This mutant was then used to crystallize the VHH-ASC CARD complex. The study revealed a 4.2 Å resolution structure of the VHH-ASC CARD complex, showing that VHH blocks the Type II interface of ASC, thereby restricting the recruitment of the caspase-1 CARD domain and ultimately preventing inflammasome activation³⁰. In a recent study, ASC PYD domain was crystallized with a protein binder specific to the PYD domain. This protein binder called 'repebody' (rB7) contains leucine-rich-repeat (LRR) modules and ~30kDa in molecular weight. The rB7 showed high affinity and specificity for the ASC PYD domain. In order

to crystallize the rB7-ASC PYD complex, ten residues were removed from the C-terminus of ASC PYD domain. This study showed that rB7 disrupts the ASC oligomerization and interaction of rB7 with ASC speck increased the activation of caspase-1 due to the ASC CARD-caspase^{31,32}.

ASC can form both homo and hetero oligomeric assemblies, but the PYD and CARD domain do not interact with each other. For the inflammasome assembly, the ASC acts as molecular glue, where the CARD domain interacts with the CARD domain of the procaspase-1 and PYD domain interacts with the PYD domain of NLR sensor proteins²⁹.

Assays to evaluate ASC targeting molecules

Due to its central role in organizing inflammasomes², we have nominated ASC as a target for the treatment of AD. The development of drug-like molecules that interact with ASC would have broad therapeutic potential in AD, mitigating neuroinflammation by inhibiting mature cytokine production, reducing ASC speck formation in inflamed tissues, and/or interfering with the ability of ASC to seed amyloid plaques, thereby disrupting several known pathological processes in AD.

To inform a drug discovery campaign targeting ASC, it is essential to establish and evaluate robust pharmacological assays that accurately measure ASC function. These assays must be designed, optimized, and validated to inform Structure-Activity Relationship (SAR) studies, enabling the iterative optimization of lead compounds based on their biochemical and cellular effects. Furthermore, for these assays to be translationally relevant, they should correlate with biologically meaningful endpoints, first in preclinical AD models, and ultimately in human clinical studies. This will ensure that ASC-targeting therapeutics not only demonstrate efficacy in preclinical studies but also have the potential to translate into clinically relevant target engagement and efficacy in humans using biomarker assay.

Biophysical assay – It is challenging to study the interactions between ligand and ASC full length protein. Even as truncated isoforms, PYD and CARD domains oligomerize and can form aggregates, thereby creating a major hindrance through protein insolubility. The only full length structure of ASC determined using NMR involved denaturing condition (5M GdHCl) and subsequent refolding²³. However, NMR is still a challenging technique to study ligand-ASC interactions because of the possibility of the refolding artifacts and of non-native conformers generated through the process. A study showed the binding of caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE) compound with ASC using an antibody-based affinity method of surface plasmon resonance (SPR)³³. Conventional SPR maybe challenging due to heterogenous orientations and Microscale Thermophoresis (MST) maybe²⁷. There are some studies reported to understand the oligomerization of ASC and with its partners using dynamic light scattering (DLS) and fluorescence polarization assays^{2,24}. But the use of these techniques to understand how a potential ligand can disrupt the oligomerization of ASC are yet to be explored. Another alternate would be to screen

crystallization conditions of ligand-ASC complex using any monomeric mutant of the ASC domain or using cryo-EM to understand the ASC filament-ligand interactions

Inflammasome priming and activation – For each of the experimental approaches described below it is important to carefully consider the cellular context. A priming step of immune cell activation is often required to achieve full activation and assembly of the inflammasome complex³⁴. Experimentally, this priming step is often achieved through the treatment of cells with bacterial-derived TLR4 agonist lipopolysaccharides (LPS)³⁵. Immune priming precedes the secondary inflammasome activation stimulus to promote upregulation of inflammasome associated genes as well as post-translational processing of inflammasome proteins. Specific inflammasomes are then activated using a second stimulus, such as the NLRP3 activator nigericin or adenosine triphosphate (ATP)³⁶. Inflammasome activation initiates a cascade of events which can be measured experimentally. These events include ASC protein oligomerization, caspase-1 cleavage and enzyme activation, cleavage and bioactivation of IL-1 β and IL-18 cytokines, and cleavage of gasdermin D resulting in membrane pore formation and ultimately release of activated cytokines and cell death.

ASC Aggregation and Imaging Assays – When cells are appropriately stimulated to trigger an inflammasome, ASC protein reorganizes from a broad cellular distribution to organized intracellular aggregates or specks. The aggregation of ASC is directly related to its biological function as a scaffolding protein in the inflammasome and can be measured as an upstream readout of inflammasome activation³⁷. These ASC aggregates can be quantified using immunofluorescent imaging³. The ASC protein can also be genetically tagged with a fluorescent protein, or a fluorescent tagged ASC can be overexpressed to visualize specks³⁷. A transgenic mouse with a fluorescently labeled ASC protein allows for visualization and quantification of ASC specks in tissues³⁸. Fluorescent ASC aggregation assays may be particularly amenable to high-content imaging experiments. ASC aggregates can be immunolabeled in paraformaldehyde fixed cells and imaged, or a modified fluorescent-tagged ASC cell lines utilized for live-cell imaging assays. Screening of ASC aggregation can be conducted by inducing inflammasome activation by priming and activation stimuli and then imaging and counting cells for ASC specks.

Caspase 1 cleavage and activity assays – The inflammasome has been described as a caspase-1 activation platform³⁹. Inflammasome formation results in caspase-1 recruitment and autocatalytic activation of the caspase zymogen. Western blots of caspase cleavage serve as a useful indicator of inflammasome activation or inhibition by measuring the molecular size of caspase proteins. Practically, this can be accomplished by utilizing assays such as the Caspase-Glo[®] 1 Inflammasome Assay in which caspase-1 proteolytic activity results in the generation of luciferase substrates for luminescent readouts⁴⁰.

IL-1 β and IL-18 assays – The cleavage and release of IL-1 β and IL-18 by is mediated by the inflammasome and can be measured in the conditioned media of stimulated cells. The release of these activated cytokines is enhanced by the formation of gasdermin D pores⁴¹. IL-1 β and IL-18 levels in conditioned media or other biological samples can be measured by ELISA. Standard

western blotting can also be used to assess the levels of both immature IL-1 β and its cleaved active forms.

Pyroptosis Assays – Inflammatory cell death or pyroptosis can occur as a result of inflammasome activation and membrane pore formation⁶. Screening for cell death is performed by imaging using reagents such as fluorescent dyes or Hoechst nuclei imaging. Cell death screening can also be multiplexed with other assays by using fluorescent cytotoxicity assay reagents. The secreted contents of pyroptotic cells, such as lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), can also be measured in conditioned media⁴².

Microglia and myeloid cell models – Most inflammasome and ASC research in the context of the brain has been performed in microglia and other myeloid cells and models. Myeloid cell lines that can be used in the assays described above include THP-1 monocytes, and the BV2 and SIM-A9 microglial lines^{5,43-45}. Primary mouse microglia or iPSC derived microglia can serve as a valuable second screening tool to validate results obtained with tool molecules against ASC in cell lines. Assay development for ASC using these myeloid cell lines and iPSC microglia can first be assessed for the levels of ASC protein under control and primed activation states. Inflammasome activation should also be confirmed using different stimuli including nigericin and ATP and measuring IL-1B release and cell death.

Phenotypic screening for ASC targeting molecules in cell lines can be performed initially by measuring cell populations containing induced ASC specks through high content fluorescent imaging. Tool molecules which bind ASC may disrupt ASC aggregation and speck formation leading to reduced numbers of ASC speck positive cells in screens. Tool molecules may also interfere with ASC mediated caspase-1 recruitment and activation by binding to the ASC CARD domain. Caspase-1 activity can be screened by measuring IL-1 β and IL-18 in conditioned media. It is possible that different *in vitro* phenotypic assays may identify varying IC50 concentrations are required to efficiently inhibit each of these inflammasome readouts described above.

Animal models – Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic (PK/PD) studies involve oral administration or intraperitoneal injection of compounds into rodent models to determine compound levels in plasma and tissue compartments. In particular, for use in models of AD, the brain levels of compounds require careful consideration as they will need to reach sufficient concentration in the brain to disrupt ASC inflammasomes.

Fluorescent ASC reporter mice may be of value in assessing the ability of ASC tool compounds to change ASC protein levels or interfere with ASC speck formation. These mice show increased ASC speck formation which when imaged manifests as a bright fluorescent puncta in inflamed tissues. Primary cell cultures of microglia and other brain cells from this animal model may also be of value for development of ASC speck assays in non-immortalized cells.

NLRP3 Inflammasomes can be activated *in vivo* by administering an intraperitoneal (IP) injection of LPS for inflammasome priming followed by an IP injection of ATP resulting in a potent release of IL-1 β into blood and tissues. This particular strategy has been utilized in previous research to provide *in vivo* validate NLRP3 inhibitors⁴⁶. Similar approaches will be of value in screening for ASC inhibitors as IL-1 β release is a downstream effect of various inflammasomes and is a consequence of caspase-1 activation. Measurements of IL-18 levels may provide additional value as expression of this cytokine is less dependent on cellular priming signals. In contrast to these acute animal experiments, studies in aging transgenic AD mouse models will likely require longer administration of compounds to manifest in detectable phenotypes.

An overview of reported ASC targeting molecules

Various strategies have been taken to prevent the involvement of ASC in inflammasome formation. Given that ASC does not have a natural ligand and is primarily involved in protein-protein interactions (PPIs), the primary strategy could be to inhibit ASC's interactions with other PYD-domain-containing proteins in the inflammasome pathway, such as NLRP3, or to interfere with ASC's ability to homo-oligomerize to form filaments and specks. Alternatively, an indirect strategy could be employed where a small molecule targets a protein upstream such as in the priming phase to block the expression of the *PYCARD* gene, thus preventing the synthesis of ASC itself or to prevent phosphorylation events critical for the activation of ASC⁴⁷.

IC100, a fully humanized monoclonal antibody (mAb) developed by ZyVersa Therapeutics^{48,49}. IC100 targets has demonstrated the ability to penetrate the brain and even enter cells via the FcRn-mediated antibody recycling pathway, and once inside cells, IC100 interferes with ASC polymerization, preventing the assembly of ASC specks, which are essential for inflammasome activation. This inhibition leads to a significant reduction in IL-1 β release in human whole blood, an important marker of inflammasome activity and systemic inflammation.

AC Immune presented their work on ACI-6635 at the ADPD conference in 2024. This mAb has shown cross-reactivity in mouse and human. The reported mechanism of action involves exploiting its IgG effector function to increase the phagocytic uptake of ASC aggregates, thus lowering the seeding potential of ASC specks to form amyloid beta plaques. Further, ACI-6635 reduced Iba1 and GFAP in AD mouse models.

The antibody fragment VHH_{ASC} targets the CARD domain of human ASC to prevent oligomerization and speck formation³⁰. This inhibition was found to lead to a significant reduction in NLRP3, AIM2 and NAIP inflammasome mediated IL-1 β release.

Another method to target ASC disruption is the use of a binding protein such as rB7³². One such This 30 kD protein was identified using a phage display against the ASC PYD domain. rB7 is capable of disassembling ASC specks into smaller oligomers. Surprisingly, these smaller ASC oligomers had high caspase-1 activity, potentially suggesting a role for specific ASC aggregation states in

regulating the activity of caspase-1, possibly through improved recruitment of caspase-1 through the exposure of CARD domains.

Small molecules also provide viable approaches in targeting ASC protein (**Figure 6**)⁵⁰. Apigenin⁵¹, a flavonoid polyphenol natural product, is one such molecule that reportedly inhibits ASC oligomerization indirectly by blocking the phosphorylation of key residues, such as mTyr144 (equivalent to hTyr146), by Syk or Pyk2 kinases, preventing the activation of ASC and the formation of NLRP3 and AIM2 inflammasomes⁴⁷. Apigenin does not appear to directly bind ASC but rather interrupts upstream signaling mechanisms⁵². Similar effects have been observed with *Artemisia princeps* extract (APO),⁵³ whose anti-inflammatory effects have typically been attributed to chlorogenic acid. APO inhibits the formation of ASC specks by blocking mTyr144 phosphorylation in both NLRP3 and AIM2 inflammasomes. Interestingly, neither Apigenin nor APO affects the NLRC4 inflammasome, indicating some degree of specificity among the various inflammasome pathways. The small molecule safranal has also been shown to disrupt ASC oligomerization and speck formation and ultimately prevent IL-1 β cleavage⁵⁴. Selectivity was observed with only the NLRP3 inflammasome being affected and not AIM2. These effects are most likely due to upstream events such as upregulation of NRF2.

Figure 6. Chemical structures for reported inhibitors of ASC function.

Another small molecule, caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE), shows more direct effects on ASC.³³ CAPE binds to ASC as seen by surface plasmon resonance (SPR) analysis, presumably at the PYD domain. Additionally, CAPE had no impact the mRNA levels of *PYCARD*, indicating that the mechanism of action is solely associated with the protein itself. Treatment of primary mouse macrophages resulted in suppressed monosodium urate (MSU) crystals-induced caspase-1 activation and IL-1 β production with similar results observed in *in vivo* mouse models. The formation of ASC specks was also diminished.

It is important to note that polyphenols like apigenin and CAPE are known for their non-selectivity⁵⁵. In general flavonoids like apigenin bind various proteins, acting as inhibitors, activators, or modulators. Although this polypharmacology can drive anti-inflammatory effects in cellular models and even *in vivo*, it also poses challenges. Targeting multiple pathways complicates the precise mechanistic studies required for target enablement and risks undesired

pharmacology. For example, apigenin is also to be involved in many other cellular pathways including inhibition of monoamine oxidase-A and B,⁵⁶ elevating NAD⁺ levels by the inhibition of CD38,⁵⁷ downregulation of cyclin-dependent kinase 1 (CDK1) expression via ribosomal protein S9 (RPS9) inhibition,⁵⁸ and a wide variety of cancer and inflammation related pathways though the exact cell targets remain unclear.^{59,60} Chlorogenic acid has been shown to bind to COX2⁶¹ and lipoxygenases,⁶² and is implicated in modulating the activity of AKR1B10,⁶³ AMPK,⁶⁴ and tyrosinase⁶⁵ enzymes. Unfortunately, the use of CAPE as a molecular probe is also complicated by polypharmacology and poor drug-like properties. Although CAPE did show direct binding to ASC, it has also been reported to impact other inflammation related targets such as NFκB⁶⁶ and nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2).^{67,68}

MM01, discovered through screening for pro-Caspase-1 activation, inhibits ASC participation by preventing oligomerization presumably by directly binding to the PYD domain.^{69,70} Activated THP-1 cells treated with MM01 had impaired IL-1β release and reduced cell death compared to controls, demonstrating MM01 is sufficient to reduce inflammasome activation of pyroptosis in vitro. Interestingly, MM01 also leads to a decrease in ASC protein levels, although it does not affect *PYCARD* mRNA levels, suggesting that it may trigger ASC degradation. Despite its promising activity, MM01 contains a rhodamine ring, a notorious PAINS (pan assay interference compounds)⁷¹ making it unacceptable as a starting point for a drug discovery campaign. Furthermore, MM01 shares a core structure with ClpB inhibitor antimicrobials⁷² which raises selectivity concerns.

Reducing the levels of the ASC protein is another viable strategy to limit inflammasome activity. This concept is seen by inhibition of the NF-κB pathway in the priming stage which reduces the expression of NLRP3⁵⁰. Lower *PYCARD* expression was also observed in the treatment of MM01⁷⁰. Another powerful method to achieve a reduction in protein levels would be the utilization of siRNA or antisense oligonucleotides. Intrathecal administration of the siRNA could be particularly effective in avoiding immune suppression in the periphery. Conveniently, *PYCARD* siRNA and related materials are already commercially available (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, sc-37282). The use of *PYCARD* siRNA has already been shown to reduce secretion of IL-1β^{73,74}. *PYCARD* knockdown in BV2 cells caused significantly reduced NLRP3 and NF-κB levels and inhibited the cleavage of GSDMD, and release of caspase-1, IL-1 β and IL-18.⁷⁵ Furthermore, treatment of co-cultured SH-SY5Y cells with *PYCARD* siRNA-transfected BV2 cells resulted in lower α-synuclein levels.

Discussion & Future Directions

Direct ASC target modulators exert their biological effects by binding to the PYD or CARD domains on the ASC protein and preventing ASC recruitment and aggregation. This will reduce the recruitment and activation of caspase-1 and prevent the formation of the activated inflammasome and ASC specks. This will also inhibit both IL-1β and IL-18 cytokine activation and

release from cells. Moreover, this may prevent the formation of gasdermin pores, which have recently been shown to have the ability to transfer across cells to propagate cell death⁷⁶.

While this review has largely focused on myeloid cells, microglia are not the only cells in the central nervous system that have been shown to exhibit inflammasome biology. Human astrocytes have been shown to express the inflammasome sensor NLRP2⁷⁷. Inflammasome components including ASC have been detected in oligodendrocytes and may play a role in demyelinating disease^{78,79}. There may be unanticipated consequences for disrupting ASC aggregate assembly *in vivo*, as the AIM2 inflammasome has been shown to play an important role in brain development by detecting damaged neuronal DNA for clearance⁸⁰. ASC inhibition may also lead to increased susceptibility to infections, as inflammasomes have been shown to be beneficial against foreign pathogens including toxoplasma and bacteria^{81,82}.

ASC is an attractive target for developing new tool molecules for modulation of neuroinflammation because of its central role in the organization of inflammasomes, independent of the initial triggering receptor. Drug-like molecules against ASC can be tested and validated *in vivo* using acute inflammation models, such as those used in prior studies of NLRP3 inhibitors⁸³, before conducting longer costly studies in aged AD mice.

Given the progress already made by ZyVersa on the IC100 antibody, future academic advancements should be focused on the exploration of siRNA in AD models and the development of small molecule inhibitors. The available siRNA could quickly be validated for *PYCARD* knock-down, followed by *in vivo* studies in AD mouse models looking specifically at IL-1 β levels.

Attempts could be made to improve the existing small molecules but given the apparent lack of selectivity and the similarity to PAINS substructures, the discovery of novel scaffolds would most likely be necessary. Spontaneous self-oligomerization of ASC would present challenges to conducting biophysical high throughput screens, though careful experimental design could allow for certain biophysical assays to be run on smaller scales. Alterations to the WT structure may prevent this oligomerization while maintaining small molecule site binding sites may be possible but would require extensive exploration and validation. Moderate throughput screening using cellular assays is reported^{84,85} but is resource intensive and would lack target specificity. The rapid advances in AI-assisted techniques have made virtual screening much more reliable^{86,87}. The reported NMR, Cryo-EM, and x-ray structures could aid in the creation of a homology model suitable for virtual screening after identifying binding pockets using Schrödinger's SiteMap⁸⁸, Fpocket⁸⁹, CASTp⁹⁰, and DoGSiteScorer⁹¹. The aforementioned biophysical and cellular assays would well support virtual hit validation and SAR studies needed to improve for potency and druglike properties until a suitable chemical probe can be found to test *in vivo*. The development of highly specific ASC targeting molecules may have value across several immune diseases in which inflammasomes contribute to tissue damage. Prevention of ASC speck formation would be of particular significance for Alzheimer's therapies given its dual role in NLRP3 inflammasome activation as well as amyloid beta plaque seeding.

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